

Incorporating Stakeholder Perspectives When Designing a Participant Insight Dashboard for an Online Community-Based Health Intervention

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ABSTRACT

Health interventions, or programs that are intended to encourage positive changes in health behavior, are often complex and delivered by teams comprised of individuals from different disciplines and perspectives. As such, the development of systems and tools for use by these teams may consider a diverse range of factors. In this paper, we present challenges encountered during the design process of a dashboard to assist research team members in understanding participant experiences in a digital health intervention promoting healthy aging. In this intervention, participants engage in an asynchronous discussion on an online forum platform that is moderated by members of the research team. User-centered design was employed to develop a preliminary design for this dashboard. We present considerations for the integration of diverse stakeholder groups in the development of collaborative tools.

KEYWORDS

User-centered design; collaboration; stakeholders; reflexivity; dashboards

INTRODUCTION

A crucial early component of the user-centered design process is understanding the needs of the users of interest (Corry et al., 1997; Johnson et al., 2005). Through engaging potential users in activities such as surveys, interviews, and observational studies, we can understand users' contexts of use, workflows, values, requirements, and desires from a system or proposed solution. When designing digital interfaces to support situations that arise in healthcare settings, previous work has demonstrated the importance of engaging a diverse set of stakeholders early on in the design process to develop solutions that fit the needs of target users (Butz & Kruger, 2006; Lyles et al., 2016; Johnson et al., 2005; Kashfi, 2010). However, with a diverse set of stakeholders often comes a diverse set of user needs and priorities; thus, the question becomes how to design solutions that meet the needs of all involved parties.

Stakeholder theory emphasizes the importance of “balancing stakeholder interests”: assessing, weighing, and addressing competing requirements of the people who are involved in the situation of interest (Reynolds et al., 2006). Markiewicz (2005) proposed several guiding principles for a negotiation model to evaluate stakeholder interests, which includes valuing the contribution of multiple stakeholders, assessing stakeholder positions and requirements, and establishing an active relationship with stakeholders by being responsive, flexible, and empathetic. These principles can also be applied to user-centered design, as it is a core responsibility of the designer to interpret the needs of different users and translate these needs into design requirements.

While the principles of user-centered design and stakeholder theory are important, challenges remain as to how to incorporate them into practice. In this paper, we reflect on the challenges we encountered in one such design process, in which we developed a participant insight dashboard to support research team members in performing intervention duties. Consistent with a user-centered design methodology (Corry et al., 1997; Johnson et al., 2005; Kashfi, 2010), we developed an interactive dashboard prototype over several rounds of focus groups, interviews, and design sessions, and then performed a usability evaluation of the prototype. There was a diverse set of persons with an interest in the project, including intervention facilitators (“moderators”), participants, the investigators leading the research, and the student designing the dashboard. After introducing the intervention and how the dashboard fits within the proposed workflow, we reflect on the implications of the development experience for others seeking to incorporate multiple parties of interest in user needs assessments and information tool development.

DESCRIPTION OF THE INTERVENTION

Aging-related medical conditions, such as Lewy Body Dementia (LBD), can pose challenges for older adults and their caregivers. People with LBD can experience behavior changes, hallucinations, memory loss, and an inability to care for oneself (Bentley et al., 2021; Walker et al., 2015). Caregivers of persons with LBD have reported feeling high levels of stress and burden associated with providing care, as well as a lack of support and resources (Galvin et al., 2010; Stacy et al., 2022).

Virtual Online Communities for Aging Life Experience (VOCALE) is a program that was developed to empower informal caregivers of persons with LBD to be better prepared for caregiving challenges. Over the course of eight

weeks, participants dialogue with one another in an asynchronous online discussion forum in which they are able to practice problem solving skills and discuss health management strategies (Chen, Chu, et al., 2021; Chen, Ge, et al., 2021; Teng et al., 2019; Zaslavsky et al., 2022). Participants are encouraged to respond to weekly discussion prompts and reply to other participants in a discussion forum. The discussion platform is maintained by research team members hereafter referred to as “moderators,” whose responsibilities include monitoring the platform, encouraging participation efforts, responding to participant needs, addressing potentially harmful or inappropriate content, and ensuring that intervention goals are being met.

THE DESIGN PROBLEM: A DASHBOARD TO FACILITATE DISCUSSION MODERATION

Moderators of online communities often face challenges related to their roles, which can include reviewing posts, redirecting conversations, stimulating conversation, ensuring platform safety, enforcing community rules, and promoting the development of a shared culture (Deng et al., 2023; Perry et al., 2022; Huh et al., 2016). VOCALE moderators experience additional difficulties related to navigating a large amount of participant data and functional limitations with the platforms used in the study. Moreover, the research team has a desire to better understand participant activities to improve moderator performance and, in turn, intervention outcomes. Thus, the goal of developing a dashboard to facilitate moderator activities was born.

Potential goals of the dashboard include analyzing and providing real-time information about the VOCALE intervention to moderators, while also streamlining the completion of certain moderation-related tasks through processes such as automation and prioritization. Figure 1 depicts the current and proposed revision to the flow of information between study participants and moderators. Over the course of the VOCALE intervention, participants produce written content in the form of discussion posts. While moderators regularly review the posts using the discussion platform, the moderator dashboard could provide information to moderators that may not be readily discerned (e.g., measures of participant activity), enabling moderators to: 1) more quickly recognize participants in need of assistance; and 2) tailor their feedback to participants, which may, in turn, lead to improved intervention outcomes. In this way, the dashboard could potentially reduce the cognitive load on moderators as they facilitate the intervention while also enabling them to perform moderation more effectively.

Figure 1. Current and proposed revision of information flow between study participants and moderators. The current flow of information is in black, whereas the proposed flow is in red.

AN EXAMPLE IN UNDERSTANDING AND DESIGNING FOR MODERATION PRACTICES

As mentioned in the introduction, the designer performed formative research, including interviews, focus groups, and design sessions with the moderators, to better understand their work and to develop preliminary designs for a dashboard. In the designer’s preliminary user requirement evaluations, there *appeared* to be a contrast in moderators and study investigators’ assessments of the intervention’s extant goals and shortcomings. Throughout their work in developing the moderator dashboard, the designer continued to view the two groups’ interests in “opposition,” with moderators being more focused on day-to-day tasks and investigators more interested in participant engagement.

This observation led to the design of dashboard features that were compartmentalized in scope. On the one hand, there were features envisioned in response to moderators’ requests for assistance with study-related tasks, such as identifying posts that had not been replied to or flagging items that needed moderator attention. As the current workflow requires moderators to manually scroll through each discussion thread to find new posts, the designer also

proposed that the dashboard could collect new posts and deliver information about them to moderators, to reduce the amount of time and effort moderators have to spend on potentially redundant work. A separate “analytics” section was proposed to provide insights concerning participant engagement. However, in the evaluation of this prototype through task-based usability evaluations, moderators provided feedback that the displayed metrics in the analytics section did not resonate with them, and this feature was not recognized as useful in its current form.

It was not until the designer brought this finding up to study investigators did they realize that the goals of “task completion” and “analytics delivery” were not meant to be discrete or in opposition, but rather interrelated. The thoughtful integration of analytic methods into dashboard features can enable moderators to make more informed decisions on the day-to-day level. For example, the proposed dashboard design operated on the premise that moderators should reply to all posts. However, some moderators take a more nuanced approach, determining which posts require more moderator attention by assessing the level of engagement of the discussion comments around it. If a participant’s post has already received a fair amount of interaction from other participants, moderators may then divert their resources to posts that may not have as much engagement, so as to make *all* participants feel welcomed within the community. If the dashboard can support the automated analysis and identification of posts that are in need of more moderator engagement, this could not only reduce the load on moderators, but also may enable moderators in the future to be more thoughtful and efficacious in their support of participants’ efforts.

In considering this issue, the question arises as to how we as a team might have realized disconnects in the design of the dashboard earlier rather than later. It is perhaps worthwhile to reflect on the circumstances of this case. First, the designer joined the research team when the intervention was not underway, and thus was not able to observe the day-to-day moderator activities. In retrospect, engaging in observation could have been immensely helpful if it had been feasible. Though the designer thought that perhaps they had become ‘inadvertently biased’ in thinking that task-completion features took precedent over the delivery of analytics and insights, a stronger understanding of the nuances of moderation through observation of team meetings and real-time moderator behavior was perhaps needed.

Another potential approach would have been to ensure more touch points earlier on during the design process. For example, the designer’s scenarios for the usability evaluation were fully drafted prior to seeking feedback. When feedback was sought, the current primary study moderator and one of the study investigators provided input that led to modifications to ensure the use case scenarios were sufficiently realistic. Incorporating touch points during brainstorming for the usability session activities could have facilitated the development of scenarios that better captured realistic use contexts for moderators.

As the development of the moderator dashboard is an ongoing process, incorporating more touch points with different study team members would likely benefit the dashboard’s design going forward. More collaborative design sessions between the intervention’s moderators, study investigators, and the dashboard designer could work to address and rectify shortcomings in the current design, while also improving the understanding of each person’s needs, workflows, and perspectives when interacting with a potential interface.

REFLECTIONS

Reflexivity in qualitative research, where the researcher actively assesses their own subjectivity and perspective, should be an important part of the research process (Olmos-Vega et al., 2023). From these experiences, we would like to offer the following observations and recommendations for discussion.

First, there are often different groups who have an interest in projects; the key groups in this work were the moderators, participants, the study investigators, the designer, and others, such as clinical collaborators, who were consulted on intervention content and provided input on how the intervention could be implemented (Figure 2).

Moderators’ immediate concerns may lay more with day-to-day intervention activities, such as maintaining the study platform and tracking participant progress. The features they requested of the dashboard typically involved functions that aided the completion of study-related tasks, such as easily reviewing new posts from participants. The study investigators may have different priorities. Whereas one investigator focused more on participants’ practice of the problem-solving skills and their experience with the intervention, the other study investigator focused more on concrete, clinical outcomes. These differing priorities could potentially result in different design requirements: the former focused on providing moderators actionable insights into participant experience, and the latter on measuring and promoting participants’ confidence in their ability to perform caregiving-related tasks. All of these indicators could, in turn, enable moderators to decide if or when to reach out to participants and how to frame their responses.

The designer plays a critical role in the interpretation and translation of user needs into practice. As someone who largely existed outside of the delivery of the intervention to participants, the designer is afforded a somewhat unique vantage point on the project as an “outsider” who does not have a direct “stake” in the outcome, which may address concerns of positionality highlighted by Markiewicz (2005) and Patton (1997). However, residing outside the intervention also means that there are times when input from other stakeholders is needed. By thoughtfully

interpreting the interests of multiple stakeholder groups and determining areas where collaboration is needed, rather than merely acting as the sailboat traveling between different islands of thought, the designer can seek to draw connections and map out potential ways forward to solve the problem at hand.

However, this is easier said than done; there are tensions that we must consider. In this context, the designer was faced with a quandary: how to resolve differences of opinion. In this case, the designer chose to “balance stakeholder interests.” While this is certainly reasonable, there can also be complications. For example, stakeholder interests can conflict with the broader goals of the research, e.g., when design decisions result in solutions that focused on perfunctory task completion, potentially at the detriment of the overall study. In this case, it might be desirable to engage in more extensive dialogue to find a design solution that is congruent with the study’s aim of improving participant experiences, while also not being unduly burdensome to moderators.

While all stakeholders may ultimately be interested in delivering an effective intervention, the approach each stakeholder takes may be different due to their perspectives and experience, and these differing perspectives might result in questions concerning the direction the moderator dashboard should take. Team members can vary in terms of various characteristics including career stage or level of experience, team member familiarity and interaction style, their field or discipline, and viewpoint. This diversity can be a source of strength (Cheruvilil et al., 2014). Our team members’ skills and perspectives complement one another, but diversity in perspectives and approaches can also lead to coordination issues in moderation and other study-related activities. We make use of communal texts and regular team meetings, where we encourage active team member participation. However, our communal texts and meetings include a significant task-based component. As collective self-reflection is important in collaborative interpretive work (Wasser & Bresler, 1996), incorporating more deliberate self-reflection as a team could also facilitate greater understanding and intentionality on the part of team members.

Figure 2. Key stakeholder groups involved in the intervention and their interactions.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we identify challenges that arose during a user-centered design process of a moderator dashboard for an online community-based digital health intervention for aging-related experiences. By exploring these challenges, we illustrate potential difficulties in collective sense-making about work practice and propose strategies to facilitate ongoing collaboration amongst multiple stakeholder groups for more effective tool design.

Encouraging active, ongoing collaboration between all stakeholders can potentially facilitate a stronger understanding of each other’s goals and collectively forge a better approach for reaching those goals. Research teams often involve persons who perform very different functions, with each bringing diverse insights and perspectives. Incorporating everyone’s perspectives is important; however, this is easier said than done. Our recommendations include integration of more ethnographic observation and touchpoints with all team members to understand their experiences and opinions on how the dashboard should be designed. This allows the designer to have a balanced, current, and holistic understanding of the intervention and stakeholders’ needs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was assisted in part by a developmental grant from the NIA Roybal Center for Dementia Caregiving Mastery at Emory University (P30AG064200).

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